

THE ORIGIN AND FUNCTION OF ENGLISH FOLK BALLADS

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Abstract: This article analyzes the historical origins of English folk ballads and examines their social, cultural, and literary functions. Through this work author reveals the history of English Folk Ballads and how this poetry type influence this country's social life and literature.

Key words: Celtic storytelling traditions, Anglo-Saxon heroic poetry, oral tradition,

Folk ballads is one of the most important historical wealth for English history. In every country early history had different types of ballads and it tells early history about early nations social bonds, life, culture. Actually, folk ballads are traditional narrative songs that often tell stories of love, adventure, and historical events, passed down through oral tradition. Because they were created and preserved by ordinary people rather than professional writers, folk ballads reflect everyday concerns, emotions, beliefs, and cultural values of English society. Studying their origins and functions is essential for understanding the development of English literature and folklore. They include various types, such as traditional ballads with themes of love and adventure, and broadside ballads which were printed on single sheets and often covered news or events, like murders, battles, or social issues.

English folk ballads originated from a rich oral tradition, possibly stemming from [Scandinavian and Germanic storytelling traditions](#) and influenced by medieval European "ballares" (dance songs). Early examples, such as "Judas" from the 13th century, appeared in written form, with later popular ballads like those about [Robin Hood](#) emerging around the late 14th century. These ballads were passed down orally, documented by collectors in the late 15th century, and continued to evolve, absorbing various influences from popular songs, music hall tunes, and regional

traditions. Ballads were originally written to accompany dances, and so were composed in [couplets](#) with refrains in alternate lines. These refrains would have been sung by the dancers in time with the dance. Most northern and west European ballads are written in [ballad stanzas](#) or [quatrains](#) (four-line [stanzas](#)) of alternating lines of [iambic](#) (an unstressed followed by a stressed syllable) [tetrameter](#) (eight syllables) and iambic [trimeter](#) (six syllables), known as [ballad meter](#). Usually, only the second and fourth line of a quatrain are rhymed (in the scheme), which has been taken to suggest that, originally, ballads consisted of couplets (two lines) of rhymed verse, each of 14 syllables. This can be seen in this stanza from "[Lord Thomas and Fair Annet](#)".⁸

The earliest English ballads are believed to have originated between the 12th and 15th centuries. Although these ballads were not written down at first, scholars found linguistic and stylistic evidence that they come from the late medieval period. Many early ballads grew out of local legends, historical events, and communal experiences. English folk ballads were transmitted orally for centuries. This means they changed frequently as performers adapted them to different audiences and regions. The lack of a single written version made ballads flexible and dynamic. Oral transmission also helped preserve the cultural memory of communities who had limited access to written texts.

Early collections of English ballads were made by [Samuel Pepys](#) (1633–1703) and in the [Roxburghe Ballads](#) collected by [Robert Harley](#), (1661–1724), which paralleled the work in Scotland by [Walter Scott](#) and [Robert Burns](#). Inspired by his reading as a teenager of [Reliques of Ancient English Poetry](#) by [Thomas Percy](#), Scott began collecting ballads while he attended Edinburgh University in the 1790s. He published his research from 1802 to 1803 in a three-volume work, [Minstrelsy of the Scottish Border](#). Burns collaborated with [James Johnson](#) on the multi-volume [Scots Musical Museum](#), a miscellany of folk songs and poetry with original work by Burns. Around the same time, he worked with [George Thompson](#) on [A Select Collection of Original Scottish Airs for the Voice](#).⁹

Both Northern English and Southern Scots shared in the identified tradition of [Border ballads](#), particularly evinced by the cross-border narrative in versions of "[The Ballad of Chevy Chase](#)" sometimes associated with the Lancashire-born sixteenth-century minstrel [Richard Sheale](#).

⁸<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ballad#:~:text=The%20traditional%2C%20classical%20or%20popular,Minstrelsy%20of%20the%20Scottish%20Border>.

⁹ Dugaw, Dianne. *Deep Play: John Gay and the Invention of Modernity*. Newark, Del.: University of Delaware Press, 2001. Print.

Illustration by [Arthur Rackham](#) to [Young Bekie](#).¹⁰

It has been suggested that the increasing interest in traditional popular ballads during the eighteenth century was prompted by social issues such as the enclosure movement as many of the ballads deal with themes concerning rural laborers. James Davey has suggested that the common themes of sailing and naval battles may also have prompted the use (at least in England) of popular ballads as naval recruitment tools.

Key work on the traditional ballad was undertaken in the late 19th century in Denmark by [Svend Grundtvig](#) and for England and Scotland by the Harvard professor [Francis James Child](#). They attempted to record and classify all the known ballads and variants in their chosen regions. Since Child died before writing a commentary on his work it is uncertain exactly how and why he differentiated the 305 ballads printed that would be published as [The English and Scottish Popular Ballads](#). There have been many different and contradictory attempts to classify traditional ballads by theme, but commonly identified types are the religious, supernatural, tragic, love ballads, historic, legendary and humorous. The traditional form and content of the ballad were modified to form the basis for twenty-three bawdy pornographic ballads that appeared in the underground Victorian magazine [The Pearl](#), which ran for eighteen issues between 1879 and 1880. Unlike the traditional ballad, these obscene ballads aggressively mocked sentimental nostalgia and local lore.¹¹

¹⁰https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/File:Illustration_to_the_ballad_Young_Beckie_from_%22Some_British_Ballads%22.jpg

¹¹ Witmer, Robert (14 October 2011) [20 January 2002]. "Ballad (jazz)". *Grove Music Online* (8th ed.). Oxford University Press. ISBN 978-1-56159-263-0.

English folk ballads emerged from the rich oral traditions of medieval Britain, shaped by cultural exchange and communal storytelling. Their functions extended beyond entertainment: they educated audiences, preserved historical memory, expressed collective identity, and influenced literary development. As a result, folk ballads remain an important part of England's cultural heritage and a significant field of study in English literature and folklore.

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